

UKBOL EXTRACTION SOP

Alyssa Paul, version 1, 03/03/2026

Prepare all buffers and reagents according to section A of the “UKBOL Accelerated Buffer and Reagent Prep SOP V1”.

Have the following prepared:

- i. **Binding Buffer D**
- ii. **Elution Buffer**
- iii. **Lysis Buffer C**
- iv. **Wash Buffer**

A. EXTRACTION PROTOCOL

Extraction (Day 1):

1. Add 200 μ L of proteinase K to the lysis buffer tubes, vortex, add to disposal trough and aliquot 90 μ L to 12x 8-strip non-flex tubes.
2. Label the tubes with the well name and numbers, briefly spin tubes down and add tubes to a tube rack that has been labelled with the batch number “**UKXXX**”.
3. Hand over the tubes with lysis buffer to the sampling team (lysis buffer left in the “dragonfly” fridge on the 7th floor). Usually done by 10 am on the day of sampling (but to be confirmed with the sampler the day before).
4. Sampling to be done by 5-6pm. Ensure that all specimens are fully submerged in the lysis buffer and not stuck to the sides or lid of the tubes. The tubes should be collected and taken down to the annexe extraction room and briefly spun down before being put in the incubator overnight at 56°C, rpm 100.

Extraction (Day 2):

5. Prepare 5 plates as follows using the Integra Viaflow (in the clean room):
 - i. 1x Deep Well plate with tip comb
 - ii. 3x wash plates: Deep Well plates with 200 μ L of Wash Buffer
 - iii. 1x elution plate: Wide Well plate with 50 μ L elution buffer. **Label: UKXXX elution.**
 - iv. 1x binding plate: Deep Well plate with 450 μ L Binding Buffer D, 10 μ L Magattract Suspension G beads. **Label: UKXXX Bind Plate.**

Reagents	Amount needed to clean 1 plate
Wash buffer	60 mL (3x wash plates)
Elution buffer	5 mL
Binding buffer D	45 mL
MagAttract beads	1 mL

6. In the extraction room, briefly spin down the lysate tubes and transfer 90 μ L of the lysate to the binding plate using the multichannel pipette. Add 100 μ L of 80% ethanol to the specimen tubes after the lysate has been removed.
 - a. Specimens can flick out of the tubes when opening lids – open slowly and carefully.
 - b. Be careful not to damage the specimen with the tip.
 - c. **Do not discard the tips** – keep them in case any part of the specimen gets stuck in the tip. (Hand over to the sampling team when giving back the specimens labelled “**UKXXX TIPS**”).
7. Run “silica v2” on Kingfisher and follow instructions to load all the plates.
8. When the run has finished:
 - a. Discard the tip comb plate (i) and the ethanol plates (ii)
 - i. Do a visual inspection to ensure no small pieces of the specimen have ended up on the tip comb or in the ethanol plates.
 - b. Cover the bind plate (iv) with a foil seal and hand over to the sampling team along with the tips and the original specimens (in case any parts of the specimen are in the bind plate).
9. Cover the elution plate (iii) with a foil seal. Transfer 10 μ L of the cleaned lysate to a low profile, semi-skirted plate and label it **UKXXX AL**.
Ensure all plates have been labelled correctly and store at -20°C until needed.